

A DEM multi-scale generalization method based on unsupervised generative learning driven by terrain knowledge

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Abstract:

Terrain, as a carrier for describing the relief of the earth's surface and representing natural spatial phenomena, provides a fundamental basis for spatiotemporal analysis and modeling (Guth et al. 2021). Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) represent terrain in a gridded form that characterizes surface relief. With the development of LiDAR, photogrammetry, and remote sensing technologies, the capability for terrain perception and pattern recognition has been greatly enhanced (Yang et al. 2023). To meet the requirements of cartography and spatial analysis at different levels of detail, DEM data typically require generalization.

Existing cartographic generalization methods for DEM are mainly designed based on mathematical rules, such as filtering-based approaches, structure-based generalization methods, and feature-point selection techniques. These rule-based approaches typically require intricate mathematical formulations, which limits their adaptability to terrains with diverse relief characteristics. With the rapid development of deep learning and the growing advancement of Artificial Intelligence for Generative Content (AIGC) technologies, learning-based methods have begun to be applied to various aspects of cartographic generalization. However, current learning-based cartographic generalization studies face several common challenges. First, the data-driven nature of these approaches leads to strong dependence on training samples, making it difficult for models to satisfy multi-scale generalization requirements; typically, introducing a new scale requires an additional set of training samples. Second, supervised learning mechanisms significantly amplify the importance of samples, but often overlook explicit spatial rules. Finally, since geospatial knowledge can be extracted from geospatial data and used to improve the quality of generated results, it should also be possible to directly leverage such knowledge to guide data generation and transformation. However, this potential has not yet been sufficiently explored.

Therefore, this study proposes a multi-scale terrain generalization method based on deep generative learning, guided by terrain knowledge and scale information. As illustrated in Figure 1, the method first extracts DEM samples and terrain structural samples from the terrain dataset. Subsequently, three loss functions are designed and associated with scale steps, surface smoothness features, and structural features, respectively. The scale step is a designed integer parameter used to encode scale information. Based on the noise generator of diffusion model, a multi-scale DEM generalization generator that takes both DEM data and scale information as inputs is constructed. During model training, scale steps are randomly sampled and fed into the model together with the DEM, enabling

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unsupervised learning under the guidance of the loss functions. Finally, during the model application phase, the level of generalization can be controlled by using different numbers of scale steps as necessary.

Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method can effectively control the scale of terrain generalization through the scale steps as shown in Figure 2, meaning that a multi-scale generalization model has been implemented. In comparative experiments, compared with four baseline methods including Line Integral Convolution (LIC)(Jenny 2021), VIP, median filtering, and Gaussian filtering, the proposed model achieves superior terrain visualization performance in hill-shading and contour representation under the same elevation error as shown in Figure 3, as well as better quantitative metrics shown in Table 1, namely the mean standard deviation of slope (SDM)(Grohmann et al. 2011), the streamline matching rate (SMR), and the average streamline matching error (SME)(Zhou and Chen 2011).

In summary, the generalized terrain by the proposed method demonstrates favorable performance in both quantitative and qualitative evaluations. The method proposed in this study provides an unsupervised multi-scale transformation framework for learning-based cartographic generalization, breaking the strong dependence on training samples that has characterized previous map generalization research. In the future, this framework could potentially be extended to other map features, enabling unsupervised multi-scale cartographic generalization.

Keywords: Terrain simplification; DEM generalization; cartography; unsupervised learning

Figure 1 The architecture of the proposed method

Figure 2 Utilizing scale steps for multi-scale terrain generalization

Figure 3 Comparison of different methods in hill-shading and contour lines under the same elevation error. (a) Original data, (b) Proposed method, (c) LIC, (d) VIP, (e) Gaussian filtering, (f) Median filtering

Table 1 Evaluation results under different RMSE

	Ours	LIC	VIP	Gaussian	Median
RMSE (± 0.3)	SDM				
4.5	0.569	0.795	0.756	0.896	0.645
6.5	0.750	0.949	1.080	1.135	0.887
9	0.970	1.139	1.259	1.298	1.081
11.5	1.131	1.244	1.411	1.415	1.209
	SMR(%)				
4.5	70.31	30.75	21.06	31.43	34.17
6.5	71.41	28.28	15.19	21.07	21.77
9	69.95	24.05	12.90	15.69	16.11
11.5	68.59	21.75	11.31	11.99	11.87
	SME				
4.5	9.744	14.574	58.235	17.690	16.218
6.5	8.616	15.772	61.378	24.329	22.733
9	7.294	18.751	73.115	33.713	28.870
11.5	7.961	19.745	90.934	50.183	37.451

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